

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF CRACKING BEHAVIOUR OF GFRP-REINFORCED CONCRETE BY PRISM TENSION TESTS

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ABSTRACT

Due to the low modulus of elasticity and high tensile strength of GFRP reinforcing bars and their interaction with the surrounding concrete, the bond performance of GFRP bars differs from that of steel bars. Designs of GFRP reinforced concrete are often governed by deflection and crack control at the serviceability limit state. In order to permit single design equations, bond capacity of GFRP bars are often normalized to that of steel bars using the so-called k_b adjustment factor. GFRP bars are manufactured with a variety of surface preparations and conditions affecting bond resulting in quite different values of k_b . This study reports a series of prism tension tests in which a single long bar is embedded in a concrete prism and subject to direct tension from which values of k_b can be determined. This non-standard test has the advantage of providing quantitative, in addition to qualitative comparison of cracking behaviour as it is affected by reinforcing bar characteristics.

KEYWORDS

Bond coefficient; crack control; crack spacing; crack width; prism tension test.

INTRODUCTION

Glass fibre-reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars have been widely adopted as an alternative to steel as internal reinforcement in reinforced-concrete structures that require long-term durability in an aggressive environment. GFRP reinforcing bars have a low modulus of elasticity and high tensile strength comparing to steel bars, which leads to design of GFRP reinforced concrete members (GFRP-RC) often being controlled by deflection and crack control considerations at the serviceability limit state. In addition, unlike design of steel-reinforced members in which steel yielding is the desired failure mode, in GFRP-RC members, concrete crushing is the preferred failure mode (ACI CODE 440.11, 2022).

Crack control in reinforced concrete members can be described in terms of both crack spacing and crack width. At a given strain, it is generally accepted that a larger number of smaller cracks is preferable to few cracks having greater width. In order to use GFRP bars efficiently, significant elongation of the lower-modulus bars is required, leading potentially to relatively large crack widths at the serviceability limit state. Although GFRP bar corrosion is not a concern, large crack widths remain undesirable from both structural and aesthetic points of view. Although there are many published studies on deflection of GFRP-RC beams (e.g., Benmokrane et al. 1996, Toutanji and Saafi 2000, Barris et al. 2009, Silva et al. 2017), the number of studies focusing on cracking behavior of GFRP-RC concrete members is limited.

Bond characteristics of GFRP bars – the manner and efficiency with which force is transferred to the bar from the surrounding concrete – significantly impacts the control of cracking provided by the bar. The interaction between concrete and reinforcing bar consists of chemical adhesion, friction and mechanical interlock between bar deformations and the surrounding concrete. Adhesion and friction are rapidly overcome at very small strains and are therefore neglected; mechanical interlock is the

dominant component of bond strength. GFRP bars have often exhibited a poorer bond performance than steel reinforcing bars under similar conditions. This is due to the lower shear strength of the surface deformations of GFRP bars. Also affecting this apparent behaviour is the shear lag present in GFRP bars in tension resulting in the ratio of perimeter bond stress to average bar tension stress being greater in GFRP bars.

In order to affect mechanical bond, there are a variety of GFRP bar surface configurations available: a) bars that are continuously pultruded with deformations (typically resembling steel bars); b) bars that have deformations machined into them following protrusion; c) bars that have a post-pultrusion-applied helical GFRP wrap forming deformations; d) smooth bars that are sand-coated; and e) hybrids of these; typically of c) and d). It has been reported in numerous studies that the surface configuration of GFRP bars affects their bond behavior and, in some studies, the associated cracking patterns. There is no consensus regarding the effect of various surface characteristics of GFRP bars on bond behavior due to the complexity of different surface profiles (Aiello et al. 2007, Hao et al. 2009, Arias et al. 2012, S3lyom et al. 2018).

Due to their material properties and variation of surface treatments, extension of bond requirements for steel to GFRP is not necessarily appropriate. There should be no expectation for GFRP bars having different surface preparations to behave similarly to each other or to steel bars in terms of bond. Nonetheless, the mechanism of cracking of reinforced concrete beams should not be fundamentally different for different elastic reinforcing materials. In this work a scalar “bond coefficient”, k_b , that allows the bond performance (expressed in terms of the development length, l_d , of the bar) of GFRP bars to be considered in the same manner as steel reinforcing bars is adopted. The value $k_b = 1.0$ is assigned to bars having the same bond characteristics as conventional steel reinforcement. For bars having bond performance inferior to steel, $k_b > 1$ (resulting in longer l_d); and $k_b < 1$ (shorter l_d) for superior bond performance.

ASSESSING BOND OF REINFORCING BARS TO CONCRETE

Bond between reinforcing bars and concrete can be assessed by means of a bond stress-slip relationship. Often, the evaluation of such behaviour is performed using direct pull-out tests (such as ASTM D7913), that are characterized by a short embedment length (five bar diameters, $5d_b$) and do not reflect realistic stress conditions in reinforced concrete members. Such pull-out tests should not be used to quantify bond capacity but are rather comparison tests. A long reinforced concrete prism subject to tension is proposed as a means of quantifying bond capacity and crack control parameters of reinforcing bars. The prism tension test, described in detail below, replicates behavior in the tension zone of flexural members subject to constant moment.

Prism tension test

When a reinforcing bar embedded in concrete is loaded in tension, the bar deformations engage the surrounding concrete and affect the gradient at which force is transferred to the concrete along the length of the bar; this is the bond behaviour. The rate of force transfer, in turn, affects the transverse crack spacing that develops. For a given post-cracking strain, the number of cracks is inversely proportional to the average (or maximum) crack width. At a given bar elongation, improved bond will result in a greater number of cracks having a reduced spacing and smaller crack widths.

In the prism tension test, as shown schematically in Figure 1, bond behavior is idealized by applying tension to the ends of a single reinforcing bar embedded in a concrete prism (Figure 1a); the external load is applied only to the bar. Conceptually, this is similar to a concrete tension zone between two cracks: at each crack (initially, the ends of the concrete prism) the reinforcing bar carries 100% of the load. As the bar penetrates the concrete, some of the force N is transferred via bond to the concrete. This results in the strain and stress in the bar falling and that in the concrete increasing. This behavior is represented by relative slip of the bar. At some distance from the prism end (the development length) the strains in the steel and concrete are the same and the bond stress (and slip) is zero. Most of the length of the prism, with the exception of the region where bond stresses develop, is in a state of uniform

stress. Once the tensile capacity of concrete in the region of uniform stress is exceeded, “primary” tensile cracks form in the concrete (Figure 1b). After cracking, the slip that occurs between the concrete and the reinforcing bar at the crack location relieves the tensile stress in the concrete adjacent to the crack.

As in a flexural member, at the crack locations the applied load is resisted entirely by the bar and the tensile stress in the bar is $f_b = N/A_b = E_b/\epsilon_b$, where N is the applied load, A_b is the area of the embedded bar, ϵ_b is the strain in the bar at the crack, and E_b is the modulus of elasticity of the bar. Between cracks – like at the initial condition – beginning at the crack location, a portion of the load is transferred to the concrete through bond and the process repeats between adjacent cracks (Figure 1c). No further cracks develop once the bond stress development between adjacent cracks is insufficient to develop the tensile capacity of the concrete (Reis et al. 1964). At this stage, additional load applied to the bar results in increases to existing crack widths and at higher loads some “secondary” cracks may appear. Since cracking is a serviceability limit state, the main interest is in the behaviour associated with primary cracking.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of prism tension test and stresses in bar and concrete (Silva et al. 2022).

Because cracking is highly variable, long prismatic specimens are desirable to permit multiple primary cracks to form from which an average crack spacing, s_{avg} , can be determined. The authors used a total embedded length (L in Figure 1a) of $150d_b$. To better compare results for different bar sizes and to better represent typical reinforcement details, a reinforcing ratio, $\rho = A_b/A_g$, of 0.0127 is used. As a result, the square prism section dimension, b , and length, L , varies with the bar size tested (see Table 1).

Due to the variability of both concrete and bond properties, the primary crack pattern will establish itself over a small range of applied load, P . Once the primary crack pattern is established, increasing P will only widen the existing cracks. Secondary cracks may appear between established primary cracks although these are of little interest in terms of serviceability behaviour. The average bond stress, τ , from a prism tension test, therefore, can be calculated as:

$$\tau = A_c f_t / \pi d_b (s_{avg}/2) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where A_c is the area of concrete ($A_g - A_b$) and, s_{avg} is the average crack spacing. The tensile strength of concrete, f_t , can be determined from Equation 2 using the measured load corresponding to the appearance of the first crack, P_I , assuming the prism to be an elastic composite element composed of concrete (having area A_c and modulus E_c) and reinforcing bar (A_b and E_b).

$$f_t = P_I E_c / [E_c A_c + E_b A_b] \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

In this study, E_c was calculated from Equation 3 (Carrasquillo et al., 1981) and E_b was taken as manufacturer-reported values for the bars used (Table 1):

$$E_c = 3320 f_c'^{0.5} + 6900 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Once all cracks are established, the elongation of the prism is the sum of the crack widths; strain between cracks is assumed to be negligible. To ensure good serviceability, ductility and continued adequate bond, it is desirable that the member develop a large number of smaller cracks, thereby distributing strain along the member rather than concentrating it at a single dominant crack. Crack width is inversely proportional to bar modulus whereas crack spacing is inversely proportional to the stiffness of the initial bond-slip response – which can be obtained from ASTM D7913 tests. Therefore, lower modulus GFRP bars exhibit larger crack widths at a given applied tensile force, unless bond characteristics are improved proportionally. Average crack width, w_{avg} , at applied load P can be estimated as:

$$w_{avg} = A_c f_t s_{avg} / E_b A_b \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The prism tension test has the advantage of providing quantitative, in addition to qualitative comparisons of cracking behaviour as it is affected by reinforcing bar type. The value of k_b for a GFRP bar type is determined as the ratio of bond stress found for standard steel reinforcing bars to that determined for the GFRP bar: $k_b = \tau_{steel} / \tau_{GFRP}$. The control steel bars must have deformation patterns compliant with standard bars – described by ASTM A615 in this case. In this way the bond performance of the steel to which the GFRP is compared, is ‘within tolerance’. As described by Platt and Harries (2018), bars compliant with ASTM A615 *de facto* have a relative rib ratio (R_r ; ACI 408.3R) greater than 0.048. Provided this criteria is met, bond of steel bars is found to meet or exceed that necessary to use code-prescribed development lengths.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

In order to demonstrate the prism test, twelve prism tests were conducted. #4 and #6 bars (12.7 mm and 19.1 mm diameter, respectively) were tested. ASTM A615 control specimens and two types of GFRP bars were tested: #4 and #6 bars having machined ribs and #4 sand-coated bars. In all cases, bar embedment was 150 times the bar diameter ($150d_b$) long. The prism section was 100 mm and 150 mm square for the #4 and #6 bars, respectively, resulting in a tension reinforcement ratio of 0.0127 for all prisms. Test specimen details are summarized in Table 1.

All prisms were fabricated from the same concrete having a 28-day compressive strength $f_c' = 37.8$ MPa (COV = 0.06), and a split cylinder tension strength $f_{sp} = 3.3$ MPa (COV = 0.07). The direct tension strength of the concrete, determined from the prism test results (Equation 2) was found to be $f_t = 2.2$ MPa (COV = 0.24).

Prism tests were conducted horizontally such that the prism is fully-supported along its length (eliminating unwanted flexural effects). The surface on which the prism is supported was broadcast with fine sand in order to minimize friction. Load was applied to the bars in a steady monotonically increasing application. In all specimens, all primary cracks were fully established by a stress well below the yield (steel) or tensile (GFRP) strength of the bars; thus all behaviour may be considered elastic. The applied load and relative bar stress at the first crack (P_I) and final primary crack (P_n) are reported in Table 1. Crack widths were measured using a “crack comparator” card with the load P_n still applied.

Final crack spacing along the centerline of the prism are also measured. Average crack spacing (s_{avg}) and average measured width (w_{avg}) at P_n are reported in Table 1. Finally, the average bond strength calculated from Equation 1 is presented.

Figure 2 shows a representative series of images of the final crack pattern and spacing of prisms having #4 bars. Crack location, order of appearance and applied load when appears are all indicated. Similar images for all twelve specimens may be found in Silva (2023).

Table 1: Prism tension test results.

Material	Steel					GFRP						
	A615 compliant					Machined ribs			Sand-coated			
Bar type												
Image of bar												
ID	#4 steel		#6 steel			#4 rGFRP		#6 rGFRP			#4 sGFRP	
Specimen	1	2	1	2	3	1	2	1	2	3	1	2
d_b (mm)	12.7		19.1			12.7		19.1			12.7	
R_f ^(a)	0.074		0.089			0.030		0.024			n.a.	
b (mm)	100		150			100		150			100	
L (mm)	1905		2860			1905		2860			1905	
E_b (GPa)	200		200			60.3		60.3			46.9	
f_y (MPa) ^(b)	400		400			962 ^(m)		962 ^(m)			927 ^(m)	
P_l (N) ^(c)	22207	23739	46308	39779	52801	19955	31544	49867	33302	49694	28138	32846
l/f_y	0.44	0.47	0.40	0.35	0.46	0.16	0.26	0.19	0.13	0.19	0.24	0.28
P_n (N) ^(d)	32930	50119	78477	93535	107832	49479	43941	84219	86187	109213	50119	43936
l/f_y	0.65	0.99	0.68	0.82	0.94	0.41	0.36	0.33	0.33	0.42	0.43	0.37
s_{avg} (mm)	173	146	191	204	239	173	190	286	260	205	89.5	127
w_{avg} (mm)	0.15	0.13	0.17	0.18	0.21	0.50	0.55	0.83	0.75	0.59	0.33	0.47
τ (MPa)	6.42	7.58	8.70	8.14	6.96	6.42	5.83	5.81	6.39	8.12	12.41	8.75
τ_{avg} (MPa)	7.00		7.93			6.12		6.78			10.58	
k_b	-		-			1.14		1.17			0.66	

(a) Relative rib ratio.

(b) Yield strength (steel) and tensile strength (GFRP).

(c) Measured load at first crack.

(d) Measured load at final crack.

(m) Values reported by manufacturer.

As expected (Figure 1b), initial cracks appeared nearer the middle of the prisms where the embedded bars are fully developed, having about $75d_b$ development length to either end of the prism. Subsequent cracks appeared along the length of the prisms, developing between existing cracks (Figure 1c). The average crack spacing, s_{avg} , for #4 steel bars was about 160 mm; #4 ribbed GFRP (#4-rGFRP) bars presented larger crack spacing, $s_{avg} \approx 182$ mm, while #4 sand-coated (#4 sGFRP) bars presented considerably smaller crack spacing, $s_{avg} \approx 108$ mm. For #6 steel bars, s_{avg} varied from 191 and 239 mm, while for #6 ribbed GFRP (#6 rGFRP) bars s_{avg} was greater, between 205 and 286 mm.

Since GFRP bars have lower modulus than steel (Table 1), they are expected to exhibit larger crack widths, unless bond characteristics are improved proportionally. Prisms reinforced with GFRP bars presented larger crack widths – approximately three-four times greater than that of prisms reinforced with steel bars; this reflects the modular ratio of the materials. The members reinforced with #4 sand-coated GFRP (#4 sGFRP) bars exhibited smaller crack widths than the other GFRP bars tested, although

still larger than those observed for steel bars. The #4 sand-coated GFRP bars, however, did embody the desirable behaviour characterized by a larger number of smaller cracks (Figure 2c).

Table 1 summarises the resulting values of bond coefficient, k_b . The ribbed GFRP bars are shown to have bond behaviour poorer than that of steel reinforcing bars ($k_b > 1$). This is unsurprising in so far as the measured rib ratio of the GFRP bars was below the *de facto* lower limit prescribed by ASTM A615 of 0.048. The sand coated bars, on the other hand, exhibited superior bond. Despite the sand-coated GFRP having a modulus only 23% that of steel, the observed crack widths for the steel bars were only 35% smaller. This difference is an indication that the bond of the sand-coated bars is superior to that of steel. In this case, $k_b = 0.66$ and the crack spacing of the sand-coated GFRP bars was 68% that of the steel bars: a larger number of proportionally smaller cracks. The sand-coated bars exhibited superior crack control.

CONCLUSIONS

A non-standard direct tension prism tension test is proposed to assess bond capacity of reinforcing bars for concrete. The test, which better represents the *in situ* conditions of bond, provides quantitative, in addition to qualitative comparison of cracking behaviour as it is affected by reinforcing bar type.

In order to demonstrate the prism test, twelve prism tests were conducted. #4 and #6 ASTM A615 control specimens and two types of GFRP bars were tested: #4 and #6 bars having machined ribs and #4 sand-coated bars. In all cases, bar embedment was $150d_b$ and the tension reinforcement ratio was 0.0127.

As expected, prisms reinforced with GFRP bars exhibited larger crack widths – approximately three-four times greater than that of prisms reinforced with steel bars – due to the lower modulus of elasticity of the GFRP bars. The prisms reinforced with #4 sand-coated GFRP bars exhibited a larger number of cracks having proportionally smaller widths; this reflects their apparently superior bond performance, resulting in $k_b = 0.66$. The ribbed GFRP bars exhibited poorer bond than steel bars: $k_b = 1.14$ and 1.17 for #4 and #6 bars, respectively.

The use of a bond coefficient, k_b , to calibrate the bond characteristics of different reinforcing bar types has been adopted many GFRP-reinforced concrete design guides and informs the provisions of ACI CODE 440.11-22.

(b) #4 steel-1; $s_{avg} = 173$ mm

(b) #4-rGFRP-2; $s_{avg} = 204$ mm

(c) #4-sGFRP-2; $s_{avg} = 127$ mm

Figure 2: Representative crack patterns of #4 prism test; prism is 1905 mm long in each case.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.